

Intrinsic Geometry of the Special Equations in Galilean 3–Space G_3

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Abstract: In this study, we investigate a general intrinsic geometry in 3-dimensional Galilean space G_3 . Then, we obtain some special equations by using intrinsic derivatives of orthonormal triad in G_3 .

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§1. Introduction

A Galilean space is a three dimensional complex projective space, where $\{w, f, I_1, I_2\}$ consists of a real plane w (the absolute plane), real line $f \subset w$ (the absolute line) and two complex conjugate points $I_1, I_2 \in f$ (the absolute points). We shall take as a real model of the space G_3 , a real projective space P_3 with the absolute $\{w, f\}$ consisting of a real plane $w \subset G_3$ and a real line $f \subset w$ on which an elliptic involution ε has been defined. The Galilean scalar product between two vectors $a = (a_1, a_2, a_3)$ and $b = (b_1, b_2, b_3)$ is defined [3]

$$(a.b)_G = \begin{cases} a_1 b_1, & \text{if } a_1 \neq 0 \text{ or } b_1 \neq 0, \\ a_2 b_2 + a_3 b_3, & \text{if } a_1 = b_1 = 0. \end{cases}$$

and the Galilean vector product is defined

$$(a \wedge b)_G = \begin{cases} \begin{vmatrix} 0 & e_2 & e_3 \\ a_1 & a_2 & a_3 \\ b_1 & b_2 & b_3 \end{vmatrix}, & \text{if } a_1 \neq 0 \text{ or } b_1 \neq 0, \\ \begin{vmatrix} e_1 & e_2 & e_3 \\ a_1 & a_2 & a_3 \\ b_1 & b_2 & b_3 \end{vmatrix}, & \text{if } a_1 = b_1 = 0. \end{cases}$$

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Let $\alpha : I \rightarrow G_3$, $I \subset \mathbb{R}$ be an unit speed curve in Galilean space G_3 parametrized by the invariant parameter $s \in I$ and given in the coordinate form

$\alpha(s) = (s, y(s), z(s))$. Then the curvature and the torsion of the curve α are given by

$$\kappa(s) = \|\alpha''(s)\|, \quad \tau(s) = \frac{1}{\kappa^2(s)} \text{Det}(\alpha'(s), \alpha''(s), \alpha'''(s))$$

respectively. The Frenet frame $\{t, n, b\}$ of the curve α is given by

$$\begin{aligned} t(s) &= \alpha'(s) = (1, y'(s), z'(s)), \\ n(s) &= \frac{\alpha''(s)}{\|\alpha''(s)\|} = \frac{1}{\kappa(s)} (1, y''(s), z''(s)), \\ b(s) &= (t(s) \wedge n(s))_G = \frac{1}{\kappa(s)} (1, -z''(s), y''(s)), \end{aligned}$$

where $t(s)$, $n(s)$ and $b(s)$ are called the tangent vector, principal normal vector and binormal vector, respectively. The Frenet formulas for $\alpha(s)$ given by [3] are

$$\begin{bmatrix} t'(s) \\ n'(s) \\ b'(s) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \kappa(s) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \tau(s) \\ 0 & -\tau(s) & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} t(s) \\ n(s) \\ b(s) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (1.1)$$

The binormal motion of curves in the Galilean 3-space is equivalent to the nonlinear Schrödinger equation (NLS⁻) of repulsive type

$$iq_b + q_{ss} - \frac{1}{2} |\langle q, q \rangle|^2 \bar{q} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

where

$$q = \kappa \exp\left(\int_0^s \sigma ds\right), \quad \sigma = \kappa \exp\left(\int_0^s r ds\right). \quad (1.3)$$

§2. Basic Properties of Intrinsic Geometry

Intrinsic geometry of the nonlinear Schrodinger equation was investigated in E^3 by Rogers and Schief. According to anholonomic coordinates, characterization of three dimensional vector field was introduced in E^3 by Vranceau [5], and then analyse Marris and Passman [3].

Let ϕ be a 3-dimensional vector field according to anholonomic coordinates in G_3 . The \mathbf{t} , \mathbf{n} , \mathbf{b} is the tangent, principal normal and binormal directions to the vector lines of ϕ . Intrinsic derivatives of this orthonormal triad are given by following

$$\frac{\delta}{\delta s} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{t} \\ \mathbf{n} \\ \mathbf{b} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \kappa & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \tau \\ 0 & -\tau & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{t} \\ \mathbf{n} \\ \mathbf{b} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.1)$$

$$\frac{\delta}{\delta n} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{t} \\ \mathbf{n} \\ \mathbf{b} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \theta_{ns} & (\Omega_b + \tau) \\ -\theta_{ns} & 0 & -div \mathbf{b} \\ -(\Omega_b + \tau) & div \mathbf{b} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{t} \\ \mathbf{n} \\ \mathbf{b} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.2)$$

$$\frac{\delta}{\delta b} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{t} \\ \mathbf{n} \\ \mathbf{b} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -(\Omega_n + \tau) & \theta_{bs} \\ (\Omega_n + \tau) & 0 & div \mathbf{n} \\ -\theta_{bs} & -div \mathbf{n} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{t} \\ \mathbf{n} \\ \mathbf{b} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2.3)$$

where $\frac{\delta}{\delta s}$, $\frac{\delta}{\delta n}$ and $\frac{\delta}{\delta b}$ are directional derivatives in the tangential, principal normal and binormal directions in G_3 . Thus, the equation (2.1) show the usual Serret-Frenet relations, also (2.2) and (2.3) give the directional derivatives of the orthonormal triad $\{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{n}, \mathbf{b}\}$ in the n - and b -directions, respectively. Accordingly,

$$grad = \mathbf{t} \frac{\delta}{\delta s} + \mathbf{n} \frac{\delta}{\delta n} + \mathbf{b} \frac{\delta}{\delta b}, \quad (2.4)$$

where θ_{bs} and θ_{ns} are the quantities originally introduced by Bjorgum in 1951 [2] via

$$\theta_{ns} = \mathbf{n} \cdot \frac{\delta \mathbf{t}}{\delta n}, \quad \theta_{bs} = \mathbf{b} \cdot \frac{\delta \mathbf{t}}{\delta b}. \quad (2.5)$$

From the usual Serret Frenet relations in G_3 , we obtain the following equations

$$div \mathbf{t} = \left(\mathbf{t} \frac{\delta}{\delta s} + \mathbf{n} \frac{\delta}{\delta n} + \mathbf{b} \frac{\delta}{\delta b} \right) \mathbf{t} = \mathbf{t}(\kappa \mathbf{n}) + \mathbf{n} \frac{\delta \mathbf{t}}{\delta n} + \mathbf{b} \frac{\delta \mathbf{t}}{\delta b} = \theta_{ns} + \theta_{bs}, \quad (2.6)$$

$$div \mathbf{n} = \left(\mathbf{t} \frac{\delta}{\delta s} + \mathbf{n} \frac{\delta}{\delta n} + \mathbf{b} \frac{\delta}{\delta b} \right) \mathbf{n} = \mathbf{t}(\tau \mathbf{b}) + \mathbf{n} \frac{\delta \mathbf{n}}{\delta n} + \mathbf{b} \frac{\delta \mathbf{n}}{\delta b} = \mathbf{b} \frac{\delta \mathbf{n}}{\delta b}, \quad (2.7)$$

$$div \mathbf{b} = \left(\mathbf{t} \frac{\delta}{\delta s} + \mathbf{n} \frac{\delta}{\delta n} + \mathbf{b} \frac{\delta}{\delta b} \right) \mathbf{b} = \mathbf{t}(-\tau \mathbf{n}) + \mathbf{n} \frac{\delta \mathbf{b}}{\delta n} + \mathbf{b} \frac{\delta \mathbf{b}}{\delta b} = \mathbf{n} \frac{\delta \mathbf{b}}{\delta n}. \quad (2.8)$$

Moreover, we get

$$\begin{aligned} curl \mathbf{t} &= \left(\mathbf{t} \times \frac{\delta}{\delta s} + \mathbf{n} \times \frac{\delta}{\delta n} + \mathbf{b} \times \frac{\delta}{\delta b} \right) \mathbf{t} \\ &= \mathbf{t} \times (\kappa \mathbf{n}) + \mathbf{n} \times \frac{\delta \mathbf{t}}{\delta n} + \mathbf{b} \times \frac{\delta \mathbf{t}}{\delta b} \\ &= \left[\frac{\delta \mathbf{t}}{\delta n} \mathbf{b} - \frac{\delta \mathbf{t}}{\delta b} \mathbf{n} \right] (1, 0, 0) + \kappa \mathbf{b} \\ &\Rightarrow curl \mathbf{t} = \Omega_s (1, 0, 0) + \kappa \mathbf{b}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.9)$$

where

$$\Omega_s = \mathbf{t} \cdot curl \mathbf{t} = \mathbf{b} \cdot \frac{\delta \mathbf{t}}{\delta n} - \mathbf{n} \cdot \frac{\delta \mathbf{t}}{\delta b} \quad (2.10)$$

is defined the abnormality of the \mathbf{t} -field. Firstly, the relation (2.9) was obtained in E^3 by

Masotti. Also, we find

$$\begin{aligned}
curl \mathbf{n} &= \left(\mathbf{t} \times \frac{\delta}{\delta s} + \mathbf{n} \times \frac{\delta}{\delta n} + \mathbf{b} \times \frac{\delta}{\delta b} \right) \mathbf{n} \\
&= \mathbf{t} \times (\tau \mathbf{b}) + \mathbf{n} \times \frac{\delta \mathbf{n}}{\delta n} + \mathbf{b} \times \frac{\delta \mathbf{n}}{\delta b} \\
&= \left[\mathbf{t} \cdot \frac{\delta \mathbf{n}}{\delta b} - \tau \right] \mathbf{n} + \left(\mathbf{b} \frac{\delta \mathbf{n}}{\delta n} \right) (1, 0, 0) - \left(\mathbf{t} \frac{\delta \mathbf{n}}{\delta n} \right) \mathbf{b} \\
\Rightarrow curl \mathbf{n} &= -(\operatorname{div} \mathbf{b}) (1, 0, 0) + \Omega_n \mathbf{n} + \theta_{ns} \mathbf{b},
\end{aligned} \tag{2.11}$$

where

$$\Omega_n = \mathbf{n} \cdot curl \mathbf{n} = \mathbf{t} \cdot \frac{\delta \mathbf{n}}{\delta b} - \tau \tag{2.12}$$

is defined the abnormality of the \mathbf{n} -field and

$$\begin{aligned}
curl \mathbf{b} &= \left(\mathbf{t} \times \frac{\delta}{\delta s} + \mathbf{n} \times \frac{\delta}{\delta n} + \mathbf{b} \times \frac{\delta}{\delta b} \right) \mathbf{b} \\
&= \mathbf{t} \times (-\tau \mathbf{n}) + \mathbf{n} \times \left[\left(\mathbf{t} \frac{\delta \mathbf{b}}{\delta n} \right) \mathbf{t} \right] + \mathbf{b} \times \left[\left(\mathbf{t} \frac{\delta \mathbf{b}}{\delta b} \right) \mathbf{t} + \left(\mathbf{n} \frac{\delta \mathbf{b}}{\delta b} \right) \mathbf{n} \right] \\
&= -\left[\tau + \mathbf{t} \cdot \frac{\delta \mathbf{b}}{\delta n} \right] \mathbf{b} + \left(\mathbf{t} \frac{\delta \mathbf{b}}{\delta b} \right) \mathbf{n} + \left(\mathbf{b} \frac{\delta \mathbf{n}}{\delta b} \right) (1, 0, 0), \\
\Rightarrow curl \mathbf{b} &= \Omega_b \mathbf{b} - \theta_{bs} \mathbf{n} + (\operatorname{div} \mathbf{n}) (1, 0, 0),
\end{aligned} \tag{2.13}$$

where

$$\Omega_b = \mathbf{b} \cdot curl \mathbf{b} = -\left(\tau + \mathbf{t} \cdot \frac{\delta \mathbf{b}}{\delta n} \right) \tag{2.14}$$

is defined the abnormality of the \mathbf{b} -field. By using the identity $curl grad \varphi = 0$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
&\left(\frac{\delta^2 \varphi}{\delta n \delta b} - \frac{\delta^2 \varphi}{\delta b \delta n} \right) \mathbf{t} + \left(\frac{\delta^2 \varphi}{\delta b \delta s} - \frac{\delta^2 \varphi}{\delta s \delta b} \right) \mathbf{n} + \left(\frac{\delta^2 \varphi}{\delta s \delta n} - \frac{\delta^2 \varphi}{\delta n \delta s} \right) \mathbf{b} \\
&+ \frac{\delta \varphi}{\delta s} curl \mathbf{t} + \frac{\delta \varphi}{\delta n} curl \mathbf{n} + \frac{\delta \varphi}{\delta b} curl \mathbf{b} = 0.
\end{aligned} \tag{2.15}$$

Substituting (2.9), (2.11) and (2.13) in (2.15), we find

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\delta^2 \phi}{\delta n \delta b} - \frac{\delta^2 \phi}{\delta n \delta b} &= -\frac{\delta \phi}{\delta s} \Omega_s + \frac{\delta \phi}{\delta n} (\operatorname{div} \mathbf{b}) - \frac{\delta \phi}{\delta b} (\operatorname{div} \mathbf{n}) \\
\frac{\delta^2 \phi}{\delta b \delta s} - \frac{\delta^2 \phi}{\delta s \delta b} &= -\frac{\delta \phi}{\delta n} \Omega_n + \frac{\delta \phi}{\delta b} \theta_{bs} \\
\frac{\delta^2 \phi}{\delta s \delta n} - \frac{\delta^2 \phi}{\delta n \delta s} &= -\frac{\delta \phi}{\delta s} \kappa - \frac{\delta \phi}{\delta n} \theta_{ns} - \frac{\delta \phi}{\delta b} \Omega_b.
\end{aligned} \tag{2.16}$$

By using the linear system (2.1), (2.2) and (2.3) we can write the following nine relations in terms of the eight parameters κ , τ , Ω_s , Ω_n , $\operatorname{div} \mathbf{n}$, $\operatorname{div} \mathbf{b}$, θ_{ns} and θ_{bs} . But we take (2.20),

(2.21) and (2.22) relations for this work.

$$\frac{\delta}{\delta b} \theta_{ns} + \frac{\delta}{\delta n} (\Omega_n + \tau) = (\operatorname{div} \mathbf{n}) (\Omega_s - 2\Omega_n - 2\tau) + (\theta_{bs} - \theta_{ns}) \operatorname{div} \mathbf{b} + \kappa \Omega_s, \quad (2.17)$$

$$\frac{\delta}{\delta b} (\Omega_n - \Omega_s + \tau) + \frac{\delta}{\delta n} \theta_{bs} = \operatorname{div} \mathbf{n} (\theta_{ns} - \theta_{bs}) + \operatorname{div} \mathbf{b} (\Omega_s - 2\Omega_n - 2\tau), \quad (2.18)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\delta}{\delta b} (\operatorname{div} \mathbf{b}) + \frac{\delta}{\delta n} (\operatorname{div} \mathbf{n}) &= (\tau + \Omega_n) (\tau + \Omega_n - \Omega_s) - \theta_{ns} \theta_{bs} - \tau \Omega_s \\ &\quad - (\operatorname{div} \mathbf{b})^2 - (\operatorname{div} \mathbf{n})^2, \end{aligned} \quad (2.19)$$

$$\frac{\delta}{\delta s} (\tau + \Omega_n) + \frac{\delta \kappa}{\delta b} = -\Omega_n \theta_{ns} - (2\tau + \Omega_n) \theta_{bs}, \quad (2.20)$$

$$\frac{\delta}{\delta s} \theta_{bs} = -\theta_{bs}^2 + \kappa \operatorname{div} \mathbf{n} - \Omega_n (\tau + \Omega_n - \Omega_s) + \tau (\tau + \Omega_n), \quad (2.21)$$

$$\frac{\delta}{\delta s} (\operatorname{div} \mathbf{n}) - \frac{\delta \tau}{\delta b} = -\Omega_n (\operatorname{div} \mathbf{b}) - \theta_{bs} (\kappa + \operatorname{div} \mathbf{n}), \quad (2.22)$$

$$\frac{\delta \kappa}{\delta n} - \frac{\delta}{\delta s} \theta_{ns} = \kappa^2 + \theta_{ns}^2 + (\tau + \Omega_n) (3\tau + \Omega_n) - \Omega_s (2\tau + \Omega_n), \quad (2.23)$$

$$\frac{\delta}{\delta s} (\tau + \Omega_n - \Omega_s) = -\theta_{ns} (\Omega_n - \Omega_s) + \theta_{bs} (-2\tau - \Omega_n + \Omega_s) + \kappa \operatorname{div} \mathbf{b}, \quad (2.24)$$

$$\frac{\delta \tau}{\delta n} + \frac{\delta}{\delta s} (\operatorname{div} \mathbf{b}) = -\kappa (\Omega_n - \Omega_s) - \theta_{ns} \operatorname{div} \mathbf{b} + (\operatorname{div} \mathbf{n}) (-2\tau + \Omega_n + \Omega_s). \quad (2.25)$$

§3. General Properties

The relation

$$\frac{\delta \mathbf{n}}{\delta n} = \kappa_n \mathbf{n}_n = -\theta_{ns} \mathbf{t} - (\operatorname{div} \mathbf{b}) \mathbf{b} \quad (3.1)$$

gives that the unit normal to the n -lines and their curvatures are given, respectively, by

$$\mathbf{n}_n = \frac{-\theta_{ns} \mathbf{t} - (\operatorname{div} \mathbf{b}) \mathbf{b}}{\|-\theta_{ns} - (\operatorname{div} \mathbf{b}) \mathbf{b}\|} = \frac{-\theta_{ns} \mathbf{t} - (\operatorname{div} \mathbf{b}) \mathbf{b}}{-\theta_{ns}}, \quad (3.2)$$

$$\kappa_n = -\theta_{ns}. \quad (3.3)$$

In addition, from the relation (2.11) can be written,

$$\operatorname{curl} \mathbf{n} = \Omega_n \mathbf{n} + \kappa_n \mathbf{b}_n, \quad (3.4)$$

where

$$\mathbf{b}_n = \mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{n}_n = \frac{-(\operatorname{div} \mathbf{b}) (1, 0, 0) + \theta_{ns} \mathbf{b}}{-\theta_{ns}} \quad (3.5)$$

gives the unit binormal to the n -lines. Similarly, the relation

$$\frac{\delta \mathbf{b}}{\delta b} = \kappa_b \mathbf{n}_b = -\theta_{bs} \mathbf{t} - (\operatorname{div} \mathbf{n}) \mathbf{n} \quad (3.6)$$

gives that the unit normal to the b -lines and their curvature are given, respectively, by

$$\mathbf{n}_b = \frac{\theta_{bs} \mathbf{t} + (\operatorname{div} \mathbf{n}) \mathbf{n}}{\theta_{bs}}, \quad (3.7)$$

$$\kappa_b = -\theta_{bs}. \quad (3.8)$$

Moreover, from the relation (2.13) we can be written as

$$\operatorname{curl} \mathbf{b} = \Omega_b \mathbf{b} + \kappa_b \mathbf{b}_b, \quad (3.9)$$

where

$$\mathbf{b}_b = \mathbf{b} \times \mathbf{n}_b = \frac{\theta_{bs} \mathbf{n} - (\operatorname{div} \mathbf{n}) (1, 0, 0)}{\theta_{bs}} \quad (3.10)$$

is the unit binormal to the b -line. To determine the torsions of the n -lines and b -lines, we take the relations

$$\frac{\delta \mathbf{b}_n}{\delta n} = -\tau_n \mathbf{n}_n, \quad (3.11)$$

$$\frac{\delta \mathbf{b}_b}{\delta b} = -\tau_b \mathbf{n}_b, \quad (3.12)$$

respectively. Thus, from (3.11) we have

$$-\frac{\delta}{\delta n} (\ln |\kappa_n|) (\operatorname{div} \mathbf{b}) - \frac{\delta}{\delta n} (\operatorname{div} \mathbf{b}) - \theta_{ns} (\Omega_b + \tau) = \tau_n \theta_{ns}, \quad (3.13)$$

$$-\frac{\delta}{\delta n} \ln |\kappa_n| \theta_{ns} + \frac{\delta}{\delta n} \theta_{ns} = \tau_n (\operatorname{div} \mathbf{b}). \quad (3.14)$$

Accordingly,

$$\tau_n = \begin{cases} -(\Omega_b + \tau) + \frac{\operatorname{div} \mathbf{b}}{\theta_{ns}} \frac{\delta}{\delta n} \ln \left| \frac{\theta_{ns}}{\operatorname{div} \mathbf{b}} \right| & \text{if } \operatorname{div} \mathbf{b} \neq 0, \theta_{ns} \neq 0 \\ -(\Omega_b + \tau) & \text{if } \operatorname{div} \mathbf{b} = 0, \theta_{ns} \neq 0 \\ & \text{or } \theta_{ns} = 0, \operatorname{div} \mathbf{b} \neq 0. \end{cases} \quad (3.15)$$

Similarly, from (3.12) we have

$$-\frac{\delta}{\delta b} (\ln \kappa_b) (\operatorname{div} \mathbf{n}) + \frac{\delta}{\delta b} (\operatorname{div} \mathbf{n}) - \theta_{bs} (\Omega_n + \tau) = \tau_b \theta_{bs}, \quad (3.16)$$

$$\frac{\delta}{\delta b} (\ln \kappa_b) \theta_{bs} - \frac{\delta}{\delta b} \theta_{bs} = \tau_b (\operatorname{div} \mathbf{n}). \quad (3.17)$$

Thus,

$$\tau_b = \begin{cases} -(\Omega_n + \tau) - \frac{(\text{div}\mathbf{n})}{\theta_{bs}} \frac{\delta}{\delta b} \ln \left| \frac{\theta_{bs}}{\text{div}\mathbf{n}} \right| & \text{if } \text{div}\mathbf{n} \neq 0, \theta_{bs} \neq 0, \\ (\Omega_n + \tau) & \text{if } \text{div}\mathbf{n} = 0, \theta_{bs} \neq 0 \\ & \text{or } \theta_{bs} = 0, \text{div}\mathbf{n} \neq 0. \end{cases} \quad (3.18)$$

Also, we obtain an important relation

$$\Omega_s - \tau = \frac{1}{2} (\Omega_s + \Omega_n + \Omega_b) \quad (3.19)$$

is obtained by combining the equations (2.10), (2.12) and (2.14). Ω_s , Ω_n and Ω_b are defined the total moments of the \mathbf{t} , \mathbf{n} and \mathbf{b} congruences, respectively.

In conclusion, we see that the relation (3.19) has cognate relations

$$\Omega_n - \tau_n = \frac{1}{2} (\Omega_n + \Omega_{n_n} + \Omega_{b_n}), \quad (3.20)$$

$$\Omega_b - \tau_b = \frac{1}{2} (\Omega_b + \Omega_{n_b} + \Omega_{b_b}), \quad (3.21)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_{n_n} &= \mathbf{n}_n \cdot \text{curl}\mathbf{n}_n, & \Omega_{b_n} &= \mathbf{b}_n \cdot \text{curl}\mathbf{b}_n, \\ \Omega_{n_b} &= \mathbf{n}_b \cdot \text{curl}\mathbf{n}_b, & \Omega_{b_b} &= \mathbf{b}_b \cdot \text{curl}\mathbf{b}_b. \end{aligned} \quad (3.22)$$

§4. The Nonlinear Schrödinger Equation

In geometric restriction

$$\Omega_n = 0 \quad (4.1)$$

imposed. Here, our purpose is to obtain the nonlinear Schrodinger equation with such a restriction in G_3 . The condition indicate the necessary and sufficient restriction for the existence of a normal congruence of Σ surfaces containing the s -lines and b -lines. If the s -lines and b -lines are taken as parametric curves on the member surfaces $U = \text{constant}$ of the normal congruence, then the surface metric is given by [4]

$$I_U = ds^2 + g(s, b) db^2. \quad (4.2)$$

where $g_{11} = g(s, s)$, $g_{12} = g(s, b)$, $g_{22} = g(b, b)$, and

$$\text{grad}_U = \mathbf{t} \frac{\delta}{\delta s} + \mathbf{b} \frac{\delta}{\delta b} = \mathbf{t} \frac{\partial}{\partial s} + \frac{\mathbf{b}}{g^{1/2}} \frac{\partial}{\partial b}. \quad (4.3)$$

Therefore, from equation (2.1) and (2.3), we have

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial s} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{t} \\ \mathbf{n} \\ \mathbf{b} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \kappa & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \tau \\ 0 & -\tau & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{t} \\ \mathbf{n} \\ \mathbf{b} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.4)$$

$$g^{-1/2} \frac{\partial}{\partial b} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{t} \\ \mathbf{n} \\ \mathbf{b} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -(\Omega_n + \tau) & \theta_{bs} \\ (\Omega_n + \tau) & 0 & \mathit{div} \mathbf{n} \\ -\theta_{bs} & -\mathit{div} \mathbf{n} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{t} \\ \mathbf{n} \\ \mathbf{b} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4.5)$$

Also, if r shows the position vector to the surface then (4.4) and (4.5) implies that

$$r_{bs} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{t}}{\partial b} = g^{1/2} [-\tau \mathbf{n} + \theta_{bs} \mathbf{b}] \quad (4.6)$$

and

$$r_{sb} = \frac{\partial}{\partial s} (g^{1/2} \mathbf{b}) = -g^{1/2} \tau \mathbf{n} + \frac{\partial g^{1/2}}{\partial s} \mathbf{b}. \quad (4.7)$$

Thus, we obtain

$$\theta_{bs} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial \ln g}{\partial s}. \quad (4.8)$$

In the case $\Omega_n = 0$, the compatibility conditions equations (2.20)-(2.22) become the non-linear system

$$\frac{\partial \tau}{\partial s} + \frac{\partial \kappa}{\partial b} = -2\tau \theta_{bs}, \quad (4.9)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial s} \theta_{bs} = -\theta_{bs}^2 + \kappa \mathit{div} \mathbf{n} + \tau^2, \quad (4.10)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial s} (\mathit{div} \mathbf{n}) - \frac{\partial \tau}{\partial b} = -\theta_{bs} (\kappa + \mathit{div} \mathbf{n}). \quad (4.11)$$

The Gauss-Mainardi-Codazzi equations become with (4.8)

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial s} (g^{1/2} \mathit{div} \mathbf{n}) + \kappa \frac{\partial}{\partial s} (g^{1/2}) - \frac{\partial \tau}{\partial b} = 0, \quad (4.12)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial s} (g\tau) + g^{1/2} \frac{\partial \kappa}{\partial b} = 0, \quad (4.13)$$

$$(g^{1/2})_{ss} = g^{1/2} (\kappa \mathit{div} \mathbf{n} + \tau^2). \quad (4.14)$$

With elimination of $\mathit{div} \mathbf{n}$ of between (4.12) and (4.14), we have

$$\frac{\partial \tau}{\partial b} = \frac{\partial}{\partial s} \left[\frac{(g^{1/2})_{ss} - \tau^2 g^{1/2}}{\kappa} \right] + \kappa \frac{\partial}{\partial s} (g^{1/2}). \quad (4.15)$$

If we accept

$$g^{1/2} = \lambda \kappa,$$

where λ varies only in the direction normal congruence, then $\lambda b \rightarrow b$, thus the pair equations (4.13) and (4.15) reduces to

$$\kappa_b = 2\kappa_s \tau + \kappa \tau_s, \quad (4.16)$$

$$\tau_b = \left(\tau^2 - \frac{\kappa_{ss}}{\kappa} + \frac{\kappa^2}{2} \right)_s. \quad (4.17)$$

By using equations (4.16) and (4.17), we obtain

$$iq_b + q_{ss} - \frac{1}{2} |\langle q, q \rangle|^2 \bar{q} - \Phi(b) q = 0, \quad (4.18)$$

where $\Phi(b) = \left(\tau^2 - \frac{\kappa_{ss}}{\kappa} + \frac{\kappa^2}{2} \right)_{s=s_0}$. This is nonlinear Schrodinger equation of repulsive type.

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